

Invariance, Entropy, Orthogonality, Quantum Mechanics and Transformation

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It is known that one may write the relativistic Lagrangian as $L = mc^2 - m_0 c^2 \gamma$ (1), however, one may obtain the same equations of motion and momentum using $L = -Et + px$ (relativistic and nonrelativistic for $v=x/t$), which is a Lorentz invariant.

In this note we try to consider the general case of uniform motion in a problem. This may be constant velocity in one direction or constant rotation about the z-axis etc. The notion of constant motion means there exists a variable (e.g. x or the angle ϕ) which is associated with motion (and change in time) in a uniform manner. This implies a constant classical probability $P(\text{variable associated with motion}) = \text{constant}$. Constant density, however, must include motion in both directions to avoid bias and should be linked to maximization of entropy in such a case. This seems to lead to a dynamic probability for one direction of motion $P(\text{type of momentum, spatial variable}) = \exp(i \text{type of momentum} * \text{spatial variable})$ such that $P P^* = \text{constant}$. This dynamic probability (which is complex) also ensures conservation of the constant motion momentum. We formulate the problem in terms of momentum because this variable is associated with impulse.

Finally, we note that one may use a mathematical transformation to link $-Et$ in the rest frame to $-E't' + \text{angular momentum variable} * \text{spatial variable}$. In the case of constant linear momentum (velocity) this mathematical transformation is the Lorentz transformation, but in the case of rotation it is not if one uses the hybrid Klauber-Salleri rotational Lorentz transformation.

We try to examine these various ideas in this note.

Noether's Theorem

Noether's Theorem (2) considers that a constant of motion is linked to a symmetry in a Lagrangian or Action. For example, the free particle nonrelativistic Lagrangian $L = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$ does not contain x and so is translationally invariant. This is linked with constant p in the x direction.

It seems that one may notice such symmetries directly in the motion of an object. For example, an object moving at constant v (say in the x direction) spends the same amount of time in each dx . An object rotating about the z-axis with constant w (angular frequency) spends the same amount of time in each $d\theta$ region. For motion, i.e. a generalized velocity, there should exist a generalized momentum.

Thus, we suggest that if there is constant motion in a problem:

- (A) There is a kind of momentum associated with this constant motion which is constant and conserved.
- (B) There is a spatial variable associated with this momentum
- (C) The probability $P(\text{momentum, space variable}) = \text{constant}$ This follows because the momentum is constant or conserved which means one cannot distinguish the time spent in one $d(\text{spatial variable})$ from another.

- (D) There are two directions of motion for a one dimensional line/curve. The constant probability does not distinguish between the two (so there is no bias), but there should exist: $P_{dynamic} = P(d)$ (momentum variable for one direction of motion, spatial variable. Maximization of entropy shows that $P(d) = \exp(i \text{ momentum} * \text{ spatial variable})$).
- (E) The dynamical $P(d)$ automatically ensures conservation of momentum
- (F) There exists a mathematical transformation $-Et \rightarrow -E't' + \text{momentum}' * \text{ spatial variable}$, but this is not necessarily the Lorentz transformation (as will be seen in the case of L_x phi as momentum* spatial variable).

Maximization of Entropy

A generalized momentum suggests momentum along some spatial variable and in one dimension, one may consider a generalized line, e.g. a curve. For a straight line, one has the usual momentum $m_0/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ v and x, while for constant rotation, one has L_z (angular momentum about z) and phi. We focus on momentum (even though there is an associated velocity) because it is linked to force.

If velocity (i.e. spatial variable / t) is a constant, then the amount of time spent in each $d(\text{spatial variable})$ is constant. There is, however, still bias because for a given curve, motion may be clockwise or counterclockwise (to the right or to the left). To have a completely unbiased situation, which we argue is necessary for $P(\text{spatial variable}) = \text{constant}$ one requires:

$$P(\text{spatial variable}) = P(d) (\text{momentum in one direction, spatial variable}) P(d) (\text{momentum in the other direction, spatial variable}) = \text{constant} \quad ((1))$$

We call $P(d)$ a dynamical probability because it is associated with one direction of motion. If all possible bias is removed in ((1)), then P should follow from maximization of entropy. In such a case one has $P = P_d(p,x) P_d(-p,x)$ and $p+ (-p)=0$ and $\langle x \text{ for } p \rangle + \langle -x \text{ for } p \rangle = 0$ as constraints. Here p is a generalized momentum and x a generalized spatial variable. One may maximize:

$$-P_d(p,x) \ln\{ P_d(p,x) \} - P_d(-p,x) \ln(P_d(-p,x)) + b_1 x P_d(p,x) + b_2 x P_d(-p,x) \quad ((2)) \text{ with } P_d(-p,x) P_d(p,x) = \text{constant imposed by hand}$$

Here b_1, b_2 are Lagrange multipliers.

$$((2)) \text{ leads to: } P_d(p,x) = \exp(i p * x) \quad ((3)) \text{ so that } P_d(p) P_d(-p) = \text{constant}$$

The “i” ensures periodicity which leads to an unusual complex probability which is associated with wavelengths in the spatial variable.

Conservation of Momentum

In the above, we argued that constant spatial motion led to a constant generalized momentum. Conservation of momentum, however, is a fundamental law in physics. We note that the above result ((3)) is linked to information through:

d/d spatial variable $\int (P d(\text{general momentum} * \text{space variable}) = \text{general momentum} ((4))$

Thus, the general momentum is the information in the problem and is conserved if it is constant. Given that one may multiply different $P d(p_1, x)$ s together, how does one show that momentum is conserved in space? Certainly, p_1 does not depend on t or x and so is constant in that manner, but the probability should also indicate this conservation without having to impose it by hand.. This follows from:

$\int d(\text{spatial variable}) \exp(i \text{ general momentum}_1 * \text{space variable}) \exp(i \text{ general momentum}_2 * \text{space variable})$

$$= \text{Kronecker delta} (\text{mom}_1, \text{mom}_2) \text{ constant } ((5))$$

Linear Motion with a Constant Velocity

For the case of linear motion, one has $\exp(i p x) = \exp(i p \cdot r) ((6))$. Linear motion, however, is associated with a frame moving with a constant velocity and physical laws should be the same in each. This leads to the idea of $P d$ possibly being a Lorentz invariant.

We first consider the idea of a Lagrangian describing this motion. (1) lists the Lagrangian as:

$$L = m c c - m o c c ((6))$$

The constant $m o c c$ plays no role in the Lagrangian differential equation or in the definition of momentum dL/dv partial. Thus, $L = m c c$ works just as well for these results. One may note that the classical action is: $L t$.

In a rest frame: $L t = m o c c$ while in a moving frame $L t = -E t + p x$ (x is the direction of motion) and $E = m o c c / \sqrt{1 - v v / c c}$.

One may show that $L t = -E t + p x$ leads to $L = -m o t \sqrt{1 - v v / c c} ((7))$. This is different Lagrangian than ((6)), but leads to the same momentum and equation of motion. Furthermore, it is a Lorentz invariant while ((6)) is not.

Thus, in the linear velocity case there is a direct link between the quantum mechanical $\exp(i p \cdot r)$ and special relativity. This link, however, does not hold for all general momenta and spatial variables as will be seen for the case of constant angular momentum.

We note that one may use AND (multiplication) and OR (summation) classical probability rules for dynamical probabilities $P d$. It was already seen that $P d(-p, x) P d(p, x) = P(x)$. The summation situation leads to a description of n-slit interference.

We note that conservation of momentum often appears when two different momenta interact. In such a case: $\int dx \exp(-i p_1 x) \exp(-i p_2 x) \exp(i p_3 x) \exp(i p_4 x) = 0$ unless $(p_1 + p_2) = (p_3 + p_4)$. If $V(x)$ accelerates (gives an impulse hit) to p_1 , then one should have a piece $\exp(i k x)$ from $V(x)$ which combines with $\exp(i p_1 x)$. This yields a probabilistic overlap with $\exp(-i (p_1 + k) x)$.

Thus, the dynamical probability picture not only carries a built-in conservation of the generalized momentum, but leads to weights for different impulse hits from a $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$.

Constant Angular Momentum

In (1), it is argued that one may use $L = mcr$, use $v = \omega r$ and find:

$$dL/d\omega = m\omega r^2 / (1 - v^2/c^2)^{1.5} = m\omega r^2 / (1 - \omega^2 r^2/c^2)^{1.5} \quad ((8))$$

This same result follows from using $L = r \times p$, where r is perpendicular to p where p magnitude = $m\omega r / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ where $v = \omega r$ i.e.

$$L = \omega r^2 m / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((9))$$

This leads to the question of a Lorentz transformation for this rotating case.

If one considers a rod of length L at rest along the x axis in the rest frame, then one has:

$$-E t + p \cdot r = -E' t' \quad ((10))$$

In the moving frame: $-E' t' + p' \cdot r' = -E' t'$ because p' , i.e. v' , is perpendicular to r' . Given that $E' = E / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ where $\omega = v/r$ it seems that:

$$t' = \sqrt{1 - \omega^2 r^2/c^2} t \quad ((11))$$

((11)) differs from the usual linear motion result.

In cylindrical co-ordinates, one expects that: $r' = r$ and $z' = z$. $R' \phi'$ is an arc length along v , so if this transforms in the usual linear way, then proper length $R \phi = \sqrt{1 - \omega^2 r^2/c^2} R' \phi'$ or

$$\phi' = \phi / \sqrt{1 - \omega^2 r^2/c^2} \quad ((12))$$

((11)) and ((12)) with $z' = z$ and $r' = r$ represent the Lorentz transformation form of the Selleri-Klauber Hybrid approach. (It may be noted that there are various theories for relativistic rotational transformations, but the Selleri-Klauber is supposed to be consistent with some experiments done after 2000.)

We point out here that one may define a math transform (which is not the above rotational Lorentz transformation) for the rotational case by using $r' \phi'$ as x' and $v = \omega r$. In such a case:

$$\begin{pmatrix} |r' \phi'| \\ |t'| \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} |g & g\omega| \\ |g\omega & g| \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} |0| \\ |t| \end{pmatrix} \quad ((13))$$

Then $r' \phi' = grwt$ and $t' = gt$ ((14)) In such a case, in the lab frame one has: $-Et + p \cdot r = -mot$

In the moving frame: $E' = m\omega c / \sqrt{1 - \omega r^2 / c^2}$ and $p' \cdot c$ magnitude = $m\omega r c / \sqrt{1 - \omega r^2 / c^2}$, while $p \cdot r$ is not set to 0 (as in the Lorentz case), but is $p' r' \phi'$. Then:

$$-E't' + p' r' \phi' = -m\omega g g t + m\omega r g g r w t = -m\omega g g t (1 - \omega r^2 / c^2) = -mot \quad ((15))$$

Under this “math” transformation, one has a kind of invariance, but this is not the Lorentz transformation of (3). This approach treats the curved distance of a circle as a 1-dimensional x . Thus, even though the linear velocity case leads to $\exp(-iEt + p \cdot r)$ where $-Et + p \cdot r$ is a Lorentz invariant, the same result does not hold for a rotational frame in which $\exp(-iE't')$ and $\exp(i Lz' \phi')$ describe two constants, E and Lz . Thus, the link between quantum mechanics/entropy for dynamical probabilities and special relativity is perhaps not as strong as may be suspected from the linear constant v case of $\exp(i (-Et + p \cdot r))$. One may note that a rotating frame is an accelerating one and that equations of motion in it are not the same as in the rest frame.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that if there exists a constant motion in a problem, there should be a generalized spatial variable linked to this motion (e.g. X for linear motion, ϕ for cylindrical rotational etc). Because the motion in time is constant, there is no preference for dX , $d\phi$ etc so $P(\text{generalized spatial variable}) = \text{constant}$. Probability, however, must remove all possible bias and so P should include forwards/backwards motion or clockwise/anticlockwise motion. These are biased motions, but we suggest that they are represented by a dynamical probability $P_d(p, x)$, $P_d(-p, x)$ such that: $P_d(p, x)P_d(-p, x) = \text{constant}$. We suggest that given that $P_d(p, x)$ is biased it should lead to a biased $\langle x \rangle$ and so one may maximize Shannon's entropy to find: $P_d(p, x) = \exp(ipx)$ where p is generalized momentum and x a spatial variable. Thus, this result should also describe $\exp(i Lz \phi)$. We note that energy is constant in time and there should also be a dynamical probability $\exp(-iEt)$. The dynamical probability $\exp(ipx)$ contains built-in conservation of the generalized momentum.

We show that in the linear v case, $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ contains $-Et + px$ which is a Lorentz invariant and directly connected with special relativity. In the rotational case, however, $\exp(-iEt + i Lz \phi)$ contains $-Et + Lz \phi$ which is not a Lorentz invariant according to the hybrid Salleri-Klauber rotational Lorentz transformation. It is possible to create a math transformation which allows $-Et + Lz \phi$ to be an invariant, but it is not clear if such a transformation carries physical meaning. Thus, the link between quantum mechanics a free particle is very strong, the general approach of $\exp(i \text{generalized momentum} * \text{generalized spatial variable})$ is not necessarily associated with a Lorentz invariant it seems, with $Lz \phi$ being a case in point.

References

1. Watkins, Thayer, San Jose State University, applet-magic.com Silicon Valley and Tornado Alley, U.S.

<https://www.sjsu.edu/faculty/watkins/relamomentum.htm>

2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Noether%27s_theorem

Klauber, R. Relativistic Rotation: A Comparison of Theories (2006)

<https://arxiv.org/pdf/gr-qc/0604118.pdf>